

Tumor Segmentation and Classification Using Machine Learning Approaches

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Article Info

Article history:

Received December 13, 2023

Revised January 14, 2024

Accepted January 24, 2024

Keywords:

Brain tumor

Pancreatic tumor

DBCWMF

HVR segmentation

CTSIFT extraction

ABSTRACT

Medical image processing has recently developed progressively in terms of methodologies and applications to increase serviceability in health care management. Modern medical image processing employs various methods to diagnose tumors due to the burgeoning demand in the related industry. This study uses the PG-DBCWMF, the HV area method, and CTSIFT extraction to identify brain tumors that have been combined with pancreatic tumors. In terms of efficiency, precision, creativity, and other factors, these strategies offer improved performance in therapeutic settings. The three techniques, PG-DBCWMF, HV region algorithm, and CTSIFT extraction, are combined in the suggested method. The PG-DBCWMF (Patch Group Decision Couple Window Median Filter) works well in the preprocessing stage and eliminates noise. The HV region technique precisely calculates the vertical and horizontal angles of the known images. CTSIFT is a feature extraction method that recognizes the area of tumor images that is impacted. The brain tumor and pancreatic tumor databases, which produce the best PNSR, MSE, and other results, were used for the experimental evaluation.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The analysis of brain and pancreatic tumors is greatly aided by clinical imaging, which facilitates manipulation and lessens the signs of the sicknesses. The quantitative evaluation of the photo processing approach is the principal benefit of using computers in scientific picture applications. The majority of clinical pictures are visible. However, visible analysis by way of the observers is usually limited, with inter-spectator deviation and lapse brought on by distractions, a lack of enjoyment, and exhaustion. The professional's interpretation may also consist of beneficial electricity if the laptop analysis is conducted with the proper care and familiar feel. As a result, it permits an improvement in diagnostic warranty and accuracy for both skilled and amateur observers. Three fantastic but associated strains of inquiry have been brought to the photograph: segmentation, registration, and visualization [1]. The most crucial step in making ready for surgery and remedy is segmenting the brain tumor. But segmenting a brain tumor using a hand in a scientific setting is now not unusual. The drawbacks of doing manual segmentation of a brain tumor consist of being time-ingesting, difficult to delineate, and mendacity within the operator's arms. According to trendy consensus, pancreatic cancers are the leading motive of most cancer-related deaths. The most everyday histological form, adenocarcinoma, is potent and often manifests as an unanticipated disease at the degree of analysis, with a regular patient period of 6 months. To rule out or affirm a diagnosis of pancreatic cancer, pancreatic solid masses need to be dynamically recognized [2].

The nucleus of almost all contemporary noise discount strategies for salt and pepper noise is located on the halt of Median filters. Trendy median filters are generally nonlinear, sincere filters that return every pixel to its unique state using the neighborhood grayscale's median [2]. The median filter regularly alters each noisy and noise-loose pixel and always plays all through the photo [3]. However, filtering removes noisy pixels, leaving the closing pixels within the contaminated pictures untouched. The nonlinear filtering operation is necessary for noise detection so that you can discriminate among pixels with and without noise

[4][5][6]. To reap the goal, many median filter kinds, consisting of the AMF, perform properly whilst noise tiers are low, but while noise stages are high, the window length has been enlarged, which makes photograph information fuzzy. A pixel is classified through the DBCWMF algorithm as noisy or noise-unfastened pixels.

Along with the quick description in section three, the problematic method of DBCWMF verification within the presence of noisy pixels is depicted inside the drift chart. This DBCWMF lessens the blurring of the picture information introduced via filtering on each noisy and noise-loose pixel. Each location is an instance of a trimming filter out. But, because of negative filtering operations, this method deletes a small variety of pixels [7]. The issue above has been resolved in the intended algorithm by considering the DBCWMF. The following is a representation of the DBCWMF algorithm for any grey-scale photograph.

Photograph segmentation refers to the department of a virtual photo into various sections. The segmentation's primary goal is to trade an illustration's representation so that it's miles less difficult to recognize and extra essential. This approach is frequently used to identify a photograph's item borders. The photo segmentation outcome takes the form of a set of areas that cover the full photograph [8]. As a result, photo segmentation is critical in the field of scientific diagnostics. Scientific imaging includes a selection of issues, several sorts of noise, insufficient contrast, and missing boundaries [9]. The brain's anatomy is scanned with a computed tomography (CT) or magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) scan. MRI scans are drastically more effective than CT scans for illness prognosis. An MRI scan will not harm the human frame because it uses no radiation. It is primarily based on the magnetic field and radio waves [10]. Clinical image segmentation has a number of essential characteristics, consisting of quick computation, reliable segmentation consequences, and minimal personal involvement [11][12]. Hired the k-means clustering rules in [13] and devised an answer for segmenting brain tumors. This approach uses three principal steps: First, coarse grain localization, using the ok-approach algorithm, is observed through first-class grain localization using a nearby widespread deviation-guided grid. The processed photo needs the mind tumor area to be extracted to divide the MRI pics into two segments. White remember (WM), cerebral spinal fluid (CSF), and gray count number (GM) make up the ordinary brain cells found in one section. The brain's tumor cells are placed within the 2d segmented location. The primary intention of the segmentation method is to restrict the requirement for adjacent photographs. Positron Emission Tomography (puppy) on Spatial Fuzzy C-method (pet-SFCM) clustering technique scan photograph datasets became proposed[14].

Laptop-aided prognosis is a critical element of radiological analysis. Early diagnosis of faulty anatomy or pathological antecedents can generally prevent the most unusual causes of cancer death [15] [16]. Moreover, there's a greater chance that the patient's required remedy plan can also be traded, which aids in figuring out the patient's sickness staging [17][18][19]. Detecting polyps for most colon cancer screening [20][21], lung nodules for lung most cancers screening [22][23], or breast cancer screening with mammography [24] are the latest examples of CAT employed in therapeutic practice. However, several CAT applications significantly decrease sensitivity and specificity tiers (greater false negatives or fake positives). They have not been included in healing exercises due to this motive. This method's essential goal is to enhance earlier CAT systems by developing a hierarchical design that allows you to enhance detection's overall performance. Ultimately, this research suggests a unique technique that effectively combines with developments in computer vision. Accessing low-cost parallel computing assets and several education statistics annotated through snapshots processing units (or GPUs) is convenient. Deep convolution neural networks (ConvNets) training is now viable [26]. Both the categorization of common snapshots [25] and medicinal applications, together with mitotic detection in digital pathology [27][28], have substantially advanced due to the fact of ConvNets' custom. Current studies have also validated that ConvNets can substantially develop the presentation of CAT structures [29][31][32].

The proposed method's general structure is depicted in Figure 1, which shows that three techniques, PG-DBCWMF, HV region algorithm, and CTSIFT extraction, are combined in the suggested method. The PG-DBCWMF (Patch Group Decision Couple Window Median Filter) works well in the preprocessing stage and eliminates noise. The HV region technique precisely calculates the vertical and horizontal angles of the known images. CTSIFT is a feature extraction method that recognizes the area of tumor images that is impacted.

Figure 1. The overall structure of the proposed method

The trails are arranged in this document as follows: Section II reviews previous median filters. The creation of the suggested algorithm is the main topic of Section III. A variety of experimental findings are reported in Section IV to show how well the suggested strategy works. In Section V, conclusions are reached.

2. RELATED WORK

This segment surveys numerous strategies for locating pancreatic and brain tumors primarily based on earlier literature opinions. For the proper remedy to be selected at the right time, scientific photograph segmentation for detecting brain tumors from magnetic resonance pics or different medical imaging modalities is essential. Most drastically, fuzzy clustering way assists vector gadget synthetic neural network information-based totally strategies and expectation-maximization set of rules technique, which can be a number of the famous techniques used for place-primarily based segmentation and so that you could extract the critical facts from the medical imaging modalities, have all been proposed for the classification of brain tumors in MR photos. Here, a top-level view and the effects of a few recent research are presented. The technique for identifying and classifying brain tumors is based on neural networks. According to this approach, which uses a neural network, primarily an SVM-based classifier, a strategy is routinely used to classify mind tumors from MR pics. Rapid Fourier transform (FFT)-extracted capabilities are reduced using the Minimal Redundancy-Maximal-Relevance (MRMR) method to increase the classifier's accuracy. With this approach, accuracy has been attained at ninety-eight percent. The mind MR images ought to be divided into two sections so that you can retrieve the brain tumor [12]. The mind's tumor cells are located in a single place, while the ordinary mind cells are positioned in the 2d [13]. FCM, seed area boom, and the Jaccard similarity coefficient algorithm are used in a brain tumor segmentation gadget that uses MR snapshots to assess the segmented gray matter and white rely on tissues. At noise degrees of 3% and 9%, respectively, this method produced a median segmentation rating S of 90%. Using discriminative clustering and a destiny choice method, the researchers studied automatically segmenting brain tissues from MR pix. A new tissue segmentation approach based on wavelets and neural networks was posted in [5], claiming to separate tumor, WM, GM, edema, and CSF from mind MR images efficaciously. The method used wavelet remodel, texture traits, and the SVM algorithm to correctly categorize dynamic assessment superior MR snapshots, control nonlinearity in actual information, and correctly address various picture protocols.

Moreover, they assert that their suggested technique is advanced when compared to first-order statistical functions. This method's category accuracy for determining the kind of tumor is 94%, with 7.5% errors discovered. It offers a powerful technique that promises a 100% accuracy fee for classifying brain tumors from MR photos. This approach's purpose of medical photo segmentation and bias discipline estimate for brain MR snapshots localized fuzzy clustering with spatial records became utilized in [19]. White count, grey count number, and cerebrospinal fluid are segmented with 83% to 95% accuracy using this method, according to the authors, who quantify segmentation accuracy using the Jaccard similarity index. To address the difficulty of depth inhomogeneities in image segmentation, we have delivered a lively contour version primarily based on the scientific photograph segmentation approach [20]. The Gaussian aggregate version (GMM)-is primarily based on an automatic characteristic extraction technique for brain tumor identification. The overall performance of the GMM characteristic extraction is improved in this technique by using wavelet-based capabilities and fundamental issue analysis (PCA). The accuracy of T1-weighted and T2-

weighted MR photographs is 97.05%, the same as the accuracy of FLAIRweighted MR photographs, 94.11%.

The literature above overview has shown that specific strategies had been created entirely for segmentation while others had been created for characteristic extraction and others for type. In all the published studies, executing characteristics on aggregate technique became no longer viable. Moreover, more information needs to be recovered due to terrible accuracy in tumor detection. None of the above literature includes the overlap calculation, which is key in determining how accurately a brain tumor segmentation set of rules performs.

Figure 2. Various methods of medical image processing

Figure 3. Various techniques are used to detect Brain and Pancreatic tumor

Figures 2 and 3 exhibit several medical photograph processing tactics and methodologies for detecting pancreatic and mind tumors. Preprocessing and enhancement techniques are employed to enhance the detection of questionable MRI areas.

The primary derivative and nearby records offer the foundation of the algorithm, and the preprocessing and enhancement technique separates film gadgets from the MRI, including labels and X-ray markers. [12] After that, excessive decision MRI statistics become tested with the median filter out, with the high-frequency statistics being eliminated using the weighted median filtering approach. Height signal-to-noise ratio and common sign-to-noise ratio measurements are used to assess the effectiveness of the advised approach [14]. The first and most vital level in image evaluation is segmenting the photo. The primary goal is to apply photograph segmentation to extract the photo.

The computerization of medical picture segmentation has found considerable use in a ramification of contexts, along with affected person selection-making, making plans for treatment supervision, and laptop-assisted surgery. The three essential segmentation methods are the boundary technique, part-based approach, and vicinity-based total method. Clusters are created by grouping associated pixels collectively in line with a similarity criterion [2]. A stepped-forward cost clustering system will offer high-value clusters with low inter-elegance parallel and distinction to the gadgets in other clusters and high intra-elegance similarity, making them comparable in the identical cluster. [9] The gain of a clustering impact relies upon the technique's achievement and the correspondence degree it employs. A clustering technique's capability to actualize is another aspect of what makes it precise. Counting factors into businesses by these objects' standards is called clustering. The assignment for the clustering method is to extract a vector from the example's surrounding regions. Every pixel is assigned to the close-by cluster mean as part of the usual clustering method. Hard clustering (ok-method clustering), fuzzy clustering, and so forth are several styles of clustering techniques.

2.1. Preceding paintings on brain and Pancreatic tumor

A neuro-oncologist's tips for selected handling that are independently well-defined are required for the survival of various tumor types with diffusion of traits. The etiology of mind tumors is unknown, and an atypical increase of cells in the skull, which, due to their nature and the partial area of the intracranial void, can also result in severe disabilities and life-threatening situations. According to the investigation, humans who have brain tumors that might be overdiagnosed pass away as a result [1]. Due to the potential for one hundred twenty unique styles, a precise prognosis is needed for active and effective treatment. MRI is the approach that is most frequently used to photo mind tumor boom and pinpoint its location. Although specific strategies are being evolved [2][3], the traditional technique for classifying and figuring out tumors in CT and MRI mind pics still often relies on a radical human assessment of these images. The radiologists' visual estimates and checks of MRIs are prompted using their environment, are time-ingesting, and are subject to mistakes or omissions, but due to the fact the records are currently complex, they cannot be changed entirely through predetermined interpretation.

Consequently, algorithmic picture processing can help radiologists examine mind tumors in multi-parametric MR pics, as mind tumor segmentation and recognition need to account for enormous differences in building facade and shape. A PC-aided method has been devised to recognize mind tumors in MRI scans. This coordination uses some phases for tumor segmentation and detection: 1) An evaluation-improving approach is used to gain and sharpen the brain MR photo, and a pair of the cranium and meninges can be seen as being almost natural white in coloration while searching on the MR photos. Moreover, it's evident that the tumor, which is as sound as the cranium and has a greater grey count number than other tissues, stands out in a set of brighter grey tiers in the public of MR pix. Remember that the cranium seems to be within the form of an oval that is symmetrically isolated from the encircling region with the aid of erasing it symmetrically in each horizontal and vertical dimension. Grey stage and geometrical factors are the most effective criteria that preclude the gathering of the erase. The consistent six pixels' common gray stage is calculated and compared to a price of 30% of the average gray level of the complete illustration.

3. PROPOSED SYSTEM

3.1. PGDBCWMF algorithm

The proposed median clear-out in this method adjusts the noisy pixels, and the window median clear-out chooses the last noise-loose pixels. This approach starts the procedure at the first noisy pixel and terminates on the remaining one. Denoised or restored snapshots are the give-up merchandise of the photo scanning process. The primary motive of pixel processing is to apply a mean filter to convert at least 3/4 of the noisy pixels into noise-free pixels. Except for the affected pixels, the remaining noise-unfastened pixel from the photograph selects the window. The best pixels that can be used in this method are the disturbed ones (0 and 255).

Figure 4. (a) existed algorithm [34], (b) proposed algorithm

3.2. Feature Extraction CTSIFT

The images' features are extracted using the SIFT (Scale Invariant characteristic remodel) approach. SIFT has been used to extract the distinguishing invariant traits from images [5]. The remaining application of this technique is photographing matching. The extreme factors from the entire scale area are described using the SIFT [6]. The hobby factors of neighbors are a development of SIFT that uses a similar technique of assessing the overall reaction. These strategies are combined to gain excessive speed in real-time computing and are additionally strong enough to turn. The everyday places from the instance, which include edges, boundaries, and so on, are where the feature capabilities from picture descriptions are retrieved [7]. Identifiers for key factors can be incredibly repetitive. Subsequently, the community areas around every key point are selected, and character feature descriptors are computed from each location. There are four essential steps in the SIFT set of rules:

Figure 5. Enhanced preprocessing images

Figure 6. (a) ground image, (b) existing feature extraction [35], (c) proposed feature extraction

3.3. HV Region Segmentation Algorithm

The essential idea behind the local increase method, a not unusual serial area segmentation algorithm, is to group pixels with comparable qualities into regions [33]. The seed pixel should be selected first, and the identical pixels around it must be merged into the district where the seed pixel is located. The requirement in this situation is that the pixel is included within the place where the seed pixel is placed if the total fee of the gray fee distinction between it and the seed pixel is notion to be smaller than a particular threshold T . The findings of local increase at $T = 3$ are proven in parent 1(b), and the whole plot is surely separated into elements. The effects of the region growth at $T = 6$ are shown in Determine 1(c), and the complete plot is depicted as a place. Therefore, the threshold selection is crucial [34]. Nearby growth can often divide related areas with similar functions, supply correct boundary statistics, and generate accurate segmentation outcomes. It simply takes a few seed factors to fulfill the idea of local enlargement. Additionally, the growing system's growth situations may be arbitrarily set. As a closing alternative, it can pick out numerous criteria simultaneously. The drawback is that computations are costly [35]. The noise and uneven grayscale could also bring about voids and over-division. The final point is that the shadow impact on the image is regularly subpar [36].

Figure 7. (a) existed segment algorithm [36], (b) proposed segment algorithm

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The proposed method's general structure is depicted in Figure 1, which shows that three techniques, PG-DBCWFM, HV region algorithm, and CTSIFT extraction, are combined in the suggested method. The PG-DBCWFM (Patch Group Decision Couple Window Median Filter) works well in the preprocessing stage and eliminates noise. Figures 2 and 3 exhibit several medical photograph processing tactics and methodologies for detecting pancreatic and mind tumors. Preprocessing and enhancement techniques are employed to enhance the detection of questionable MRI areas. Figure 4 shows the existing image with noise and the proposed image without noise. Figure 5 shows the enhanced preprocessing images without noise. Figure 6 shows the ground image, existing feature extraction, and proposed feature extraction images. Figure 7 shows the existing segment algorithm applied image and the proposed segment algorithm applied image.

Figure 8. Comparison of Optimization techniques

It has been demonstrated experimentally that the suggested approach outperforms competing strategies in terms of high PSNR values.

Figure 9. Comparison of preprocessing

The suggested DBCWMF algorithm produces clear, noise-free images with impressive results at a lower noise level.

Figure 10. Comparison of Running period

Figure 8 describes the Comparison of Optimization techniques, Figure 9 demonstrates the Comparisons of preprocessing, and the suggested DBCWMF algorithm produces clear, noise-free images with impressive results at a lower noise level. Figure 10 and Figure 11 demonstrate the Comparison of Running period and Comparison accuracy, respectively. Figure 12 shows the Comparisons of classification based on CTSIFT feature extraction-based classification. The outcomes provide classification accuracy that is superior to that of other traditional classifiers. The effectiveness of the recommended DBCWMF algorithm has been assessed and contrasted with a few medians based on total filters. Inside the contemporary research, natural pix, in addition to a traditional color photograph (Lena, 512 512 3) and a grayscale image (Elaine, 512 512), had been amassed. The top sign-to-noise ratio (PSNR) and suggest squared errors (MSE) are quantitative performance metrics that have been used to evaluate the de-noising overall performance of the recommended set of rules. The higher the value of PSNR, the better the quality of the proposed method.

Figure 11. Comparison of Accuracy

$$Accuracy = 100 - \frac{False\ rejection\ rate + False\ acceptance\ rate}{2} \tag{1}$$

FRR is the false rejection rate at which a valid subscriber is wrongly rejected as fraud, and FAR is the false acceptance rate, which denotes the rate of fraud wrongly accepted as a valid subscriber.

Figure 12. Comparison of classification

The outcomes provide classification accuracy that is superior to that of other traditional classifiers.

5. CONCLUSION

The detection of brain tumors combined with pancreatic tumors using the suggested methodologies is the primary emphasis of this research. It is recognized as a successful method that may be applied broadly across the globe to detect malignancies. The suggested DBCWMF algorithm produces clear, noise-free images with impressive results at a lower noise level. Improved segmentation performance deals with each

image separately. The outcomes provide classification accuracy that is superior to that of other traditional classifiers. It has been demonstrated experimentally that the suggested approach outperforms competing strategies in terms of high PSNR values.

REFERENCES

- [1] L. Grady and G. Funka-Lea, "Multi-label Image Segmentation for Medical Applications Based on Graph-Theoretic Electrical Potentials," 2004, pp. 230–245. doi: 10.1007/978-3-540-27816-0_20.
- [2] R. E. W. R.C. Gonzalez, *Digital Image Processing*, 2nd ed. Englewood Cliffs, NJ: Prentice Hall, 2022.
- [3] T. He and Z. Shi, "Conditionally Suboptimal Filtering in Nonlinear Stochastic Differential System," *Appl. Math.*, vol. 02, no. 06, pp. 757–763, 2011, doi: 10.4236/am.2011.26101.
- [4] Shuqun Zhang and M. A. Karim, "A new impulse detector for switching median filters," *IEEE Signal Process. Lett.*, vol. 9, no. 11, pp. 360–363, Nov. 2002, doi: 10.1109/LSP.2002.805310.
- [5] M. S. Nair and P. M. A. Mol, "Noise Adaptive Weighted Switching Median Filter for Removing High Density Impulse Noise," 2011, pp. 193–204. doi: 10.1007/978-3-642-22720-2_19.
- [6] G. Pok and Jyh-Charm Liu, "Decision-based median filter improved by predictions," in *Proceedings 1999 International Conference on Image Processing (Cat. 99CH36348)*, IEEE, 1999, pp. 410–413 vol.2. doi: 10.1109/ICIP.1999.822928.
- [7] K. Aiswarya, V. Jayaraj, and D. Ebenezer, "A New and Efficient Algorithm for the Removal of High Density Salt and Pepper Noise in Images and Videos," in *2010 Second International Conference on Computer Modeling and Simulation*, IEEE, Jan. 2010, pp. 409–413. doi: 10.1109/ICCMS.2010.310.
- [8] S. C, H. S A, and G. H L, "Artifact removal techniques for lung CT images in lung cancer detection," *Int. J. Data Informatics Intell. Comput.*, vol. 1, no. 1, pp. 21–29, Sep. 2022, doi: 10.59461/ijdiic.v1i1.14.
- [9] A. Chien, B. Dong, and Z. Shen, "Frame-based segmentation for medical images," *Commun. Math. Sci.*, vol. 9, no. 2, pp. 551–559, 2011, doi: 10.4310/CMS.2011.v9.n2.a10.
- [10] S. S. C. Bose, R. Natarajan, G. H L, F. Flammini, and P. V. Praveen Sundar, "Iterative Reflect Perceptual Sammon and Machine Learning-Based Bagging Classification for Efficient Tumor Detection," *Sustainability*, vol. 15, no. 5, p. 4602, Mar. 2023, doi: 10.3390/su15054602.
- [11] A. Bal, M. Banerjee, A. Chakrabarti, and P. Sharma, "MRI Brain Tumor Segmentation and Analysis using Rough-Fuzzy C-Means and Shape Based Properties," *J. King Saud Univ. - Comput. Inf. Sci.*, vol. 34, no. 2, pp. 115–133, Feb. 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.jksuci.2018.11.001.
- [12] E. Abdel-Maksoud, M. Elmogy, and R. Al-Awadi, "Brain tumor segmentation based on a hybrid clustering technique," *Egypt. Informatics J.*, vol. 16, no. 1, pp. 71–81, Mar. 2015, doi: 10.1016/j.eij.2015.01.003.
- [13] S. Rajendran et al., "Automated Segmentation of Brain Tumor MRI Images Using Deep Learning," *IEEE Access*, vol. 11, pp. 64758–64768, 2023, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2023.3288017.
- [14] M. S. B. Dhumal and P. M. S. Tamboli, "Fuzzy Clustering Approach for Brain Tumor Detection," *Int. J. Res. Appl. Sci. Eng. Technol.*, vol. 10, no. 6, pp. 439–444, Jun. 2022, doi: 10.22214/ijraset.2022.43545.
- [15] Ashish Kumar Pandey and Prabhdeep Singh, "A Systematic Survey of Classification Algorithms for Cancer Detection," *Int. J. Data Informatics Intell. Comput.*, vol. 1, no. 2, pp. 34–50, Dec. 2022, doi: 10.59461/ijdiic.v1i2.32.
- [16] P. Msaouel, N. Pissimissis, A. Halapas, and M. Koutsilieris, "Mechanisms of bone metastasis in prostate cancer: clinical implications," *Best Pract. Res. Clin. Endocrinol. Metab.*, vol. 22, no. 2, pp. 341–355, Apr. 2008, doi: 10.1016/j.beem.2008.01.011.
- [17] P. Somani, S. Kumar Vohra, S. Chowdhury, and S. Kant Gupta, "Implementation of a Blockchain-based Smart Shopping System for Automated Bill Generation Using Smart Carts with Cryptographic Algorithms," in *The Data-Driven Blockchain Ecosystem*, Boca Raton: CRC Press, 2022, pp. 155–168. doi: 10.1201/9781003269281-11.
- [18] S. Chaturvedi, "IoT-Based Secure Healthcare Framework Using Blockchain Technology with A Novel Simplified Swarm-Optimized Bayesian Normalized Neural Networks," *Int. J. Data Informatics Intell. Comput.*, vol. 2, no. 2, pp. 63–71, Jun. 2023, doi: 10.59461/ijdiic.v2i2.59.
- [19] A. M. Younus, M. S. S. Abumandil, V. P. Gangwar, and S. K. Gupta, "AI-Based Smart Education System for a Smart City Using an Improved Self-Adaptive Leap-Frogging Algorithm," in *AI-Centric Smart City Ecosystems*, Boca Raton: CRC Press, 2022, pp. 231–245. doi: 10.1201/9781003252542-14.
- [20] J. Rosak-Szyrocka, J. Żywiołek, and M. Shahbaz, *Quality Management, Value Creation, and the Digital Economy*. London: Routledge, 2023. doi: 10.4324/9781003404682.
- [21] R. Natarajan, G. H. Lokesh, F. Flammini, A. Premkumar, V. K. Venkatesan, and S. K. Gupta, "A Novel Framework on Security and Energy Enhancement Based on Internet of Medical Things for Healthcare 5.0," *Infrastructures*, vol. 8, no. 2, p. 22, Feb. 2023, doi: 10.3390/infrastructures8020022.
- [22] B. van Ginneken, A. A. A. Setio, C. Jacobs, and F. Ciompi, "Off-the-shelf convolutional neural network features for pulmonary nodule detection in computed tomography scans," in *2015 IEEE 12th International Symposium on Biomedical Imaging (ISBI)*, IEEE, Apr. 2015, pp. 286–289. doi: 10.1109/ISBI.2015.7163869.
- [23] M. Firmino, A. H. Morais, R. M. Mendonça, M. R. Dantas, H. R. Hekis, and R. Valentim, "Computer-aided detection system for lung cancer in computed tomography scans: Review and future prospects," *Biomed. Eng. Online*, vol. 13, no. 1, p. 41, 2014, doi: 10.1186/1475-925X-13-41.
- [24] H. D. Cheng, X. Cai, X. Chen, L. Hu, and X. Lou, "Computer-aided detection and classification of microcalcifications in mammograms: a survey," *Pattern Recognit.*, vol. 36, no. 12, pp. 2967–2991, Dec. 2003, doi: 10.1016/S0031-3203(03)00192-4.

- [25] N. Jones, "Computer science: The learning machines," *nature*, vol. 505, no. 7482, pp. 146–148, Jan. 2014, doi: 10.1038/505146a.
- [26] A. Shah *et al.*, "Automated image segmentation of scanning electron microscopy images of graphene using U-Net Neural Network," *Mater. Today Commun.*, vol. 35, p. 106127, Jun. 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.mtcomm.2023.106127.
- [27] D. C. Ciresan, A. Giusti, L. M. Gambardella, and J. Schmidhuber, "Mitosis Detection in Breast Cancer Histology Images with Deep Neural Networks," 2013, pp. 411–418. doi: 10.1007/978-3-642-40763-5_51.
- [28] A. Prasoon, K. Petersen, C. Igel, F. Lauze, E. Dam, and M. Nielsen, "Deep Feature Learning for Knee Cartilage Segmentation Using a Triplanar Convolutional Neural Network," 2013, pp. 246–253. doi: 10.1007/978-3-642-40763-5_31.
- [29] H. R. Roth *et al.*, "A New 2.5D Representation for Lymph Node Detection Using Random Sets of Deep Convolutional Neural Network Observations," 2014, pp. 520–527. doi: 10.1007/978-3-319-10404-1_65.
- [30] H. R. Roth, J. Yao, L. Lu, J. Stieger, J. E. Burns, and R. M. Summers, "Detection of Sclerotic Spine Metastases via Random Aggregation of Deep Convolutional Neural Network Classifications," 2015, pp. 3–12. doi: 10.1007/978-3-319-14148-0_1.
- [31] Q. Li, W. Cai, X. Wang, Y. Zhou, D. D. Feng, and M. Chen, "Medical image classification with convolutional neural network," in *2014 13th International Conference on Control Automation Robotics & Vision (ICARCV)*, IEEE, Dec. 2014, pp. 844–848. doi: 10.1109/ICARCV.2014.7064414.
- [32] L. S. M. and G. V.K., "Convolutional Neural Network Based Segmentation," 2011, pp. 190–197. doi: 10.1007/978-3-642-22786-8_23.
- [33] M. A. Wani and B. G. Batchelor, "Edge-region-based segmentation of range images," *IEEE Trans. Pattern Anal. Mach. Intell.*, vol. 16, no. 3, pp. 314–319, Mar. 1994, doi: 10.1109/34.276131.
- [34] Jun Tang, "A color image segmentation algorithm based on region growing," in *2010 2nd International Conference on Computer Engineering and Technology*, IEEE, 2010, pp. V6-634-V6-637. doi: 10.1109/ICCET.2010.5486012.
- [35] S. Angelina., L. P. Suresh, and S. H. K. Veni, "Image segmentation based on genetic algorithm for region growth and region merging," in *2012 International Conference on Computing, Electronics and Electrical Technologies (ICCEET)*, IEEE, Mar. 2012, pp. 970–974. doi: 10.1109/ICCEET.2012.6203833.
- [36] L. Garcia Ugarriza, E. Saber, S. R. Vantaram, V. Amuso, M. Shaw, and R. Bhaskar, "Automatic Image Segmentation by Dynamic Region Growth and Multiresolution Merging," *IEEE Trans. Image Process.*, vol. 18, no. 10, pp. 2275–2288, Oct. 2009, doi: 10.1109/TIP.2009.2025555.

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